

03 On Discrete Euclidean Space

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The paper is the third post of the blog “Discrete Euclidean Space” at <https://www.conceptualframeworks.org>.

The third post is about the consequences of the topological deformation of the units of discrete space in relation to the basic concepts in physics.

Linear velocity

The constant velocity of the quantum of energy (h) as the “building block” of electromagnetic waves is the universal linear velocity (c) that shows the pass on of the quantum – a fixed amount of topological deformation – between the units of the structure of discrete space.

The pass on of the quantum is the consequence of the topological deformation of a unit with an invariant volume:

$$\Delta V_{input} = \Delta V_{output} \quad (\text{see blog post 2})$$

Because if the universe is tessellated with units that share the same basic properties, every Δv_{output} is the Δv_{input} of the next adjacent unit at the linear trajectory of the electromagnetic wave. The consequence is that reality is only observable as local *differences* of topological deformation between the involved units of discrete space. All the values of the basic properties of the units that are mutual identical everywhere in the universe are *not detectable*.

If the speed of light is a constant (c) and the size of a unit is a constant (the minimal length scale l_c), the duration of the transfer of a fixed amount of topological deformation

figure 1

must be a constant too (t_c). Figure 1 shows the transfer of a quantum of topological deformation (h) from unit A to unit B at the moment that $t_c = 1$. The topological deformation of one unit is ruled by $\Delta V_{input} = \Delta V_{output}$, thus at the moment $t_c = 1$ the units A and B will show the maximal amount of deformation that represents the fixed amount of energy of one quantum ($1 h$). However, at the moment $t_c = 0$ the deformation has to start thus the 4 involved faces of both units are flat in this schematic image. In between $t_c = 0$ and $t_c = 1$ both units transfer a flux of infinite small amounts of volume within their boundaries until the amount of deformation is 1 quantum.

figure 2

Figure 1 shows only the interaction between 2 units of discrete space. Nevertheless, all the units together tessellate space thus all the units in the image transfer 1 quantum at exactly the same moment. Although the transfer of volume within the boundary of a unit – changing its shape – isn’t between only 2 opposite faces of the unit. Most of the time the topological deformation will affect all the faces of the unit, like the image of the schematic figure 2 above (the arrows only show the direction of the topological deformation, not the magnitudes).

Energy

All the changes of the shapes of all the units of discrete space are synchronized. That means that the transfer of the fixed amount of topological deformation from one unit to an adjacent unit – see figure 1 and figure 2 – involves all the units in the universe. In other words, during 1 t_c (constant of time) every unit transfers a fixed amount of topolo-

gical deformation that is termed Planck's constant. So it is easy to calculate the energy available within e.g. 1 m^3 during $1 t_c$ because the volume of 1 unit is roughly known (the minimal length scale l_c). Unfortunately the meaning of this amount of energy differs from what we normally consider as "the average energy density per cubic meter".

During each $1 t_c$ there is no change of direction in relation to the transfer of the flux of infinite small amounts of volume by all the units of discrete space. Therefore the energy density per cubic meter is irrelevant in relation to the existence of local concentrations of mass and rest mass. The sum of all the quanta transfer is fixed during $1 t_c$, no matter the size of the volume we chose and its position in space. For example somewhere in a void between the galaxies, in the centre of a star or even inside the boundary of a black hole. Actually it confirms the validity of the main law in physics, the law of conservation of energy.

Thus if I want to know roughly the energy – the amount of change – inside 1 m^3 during $1 t_c$ I only have to determine the number of units that tessellate 1 m^3 with the help of the minimal length scale and multiply the outcome with the energy of Planck's constant.

The meaning of the scientific method

The recognition that space itself is discrete has far reaching consequences. Because observable reality envelopes only a small part – the observable local mutual differences – of our universe. That is why it is not realistic to presume that physics as a branch of science can solve the search for a consistent description of observable reality. Physics can facilitate the research because of all the descriptions of the mutual relations between the observable phenomena. In this way physics forces researchers to develop their models according to the acquired experimental facts/results.

But the search for the basic properties of discrete space has no direct relation with the scientific method. It is about the search for the basic principles of mathematics with the help of reasoning. A type of research that is totally absent in the scientific education of physicists.

Nevertheless, physics has an important advantage in relation to mathematics. Physics is more or less conceivable in a practical way. Because physical terms and models are noticeable part of our modern (scientific) culture. In other words, this blog "On discrete Euclidean space" is just mathematics but to make it more conceivable it is expressed with the help of physics concepts.

The storage of energy in space

If I expand the duration of the transfer of topological deformation – $n \times t_c$ – the flux of infinite small amounts of volume will change between the faces of each unit of discrete space. Not only the output faces but also the input faces of the units, because $\Delta V_{input} = \Delta V_{output}$.

Figure 2 shows an asymmetrical transfer of topological deformation by a unit. The asymmetrical transfer of energy will result in local concentrations of topological deformation. Although the term "local" doesn't mean that the concentration – e.g. a particle – has a fixed position in relation to the structure of discrete space itself. The universal velocity of the topological deformation of every unit is the constant speed of light (c) thus the concentration has a velocity and will never be in rest in relation to the structure of discrete space. In other words, the velocity of the particle depends on the required amount of time to transfer all the involved quanta of the local concentration of energy.

It shows that our concept of speed in classical mechanics is directly related to the phenomenological point of view. It is the assumption that phenomena like objects have a distinct speed on their own. However, every change of energy of the individual units in our universe have the speed of light (c). The different velocity of an object is caused by the idea that the object is an independent unity. That means that the concepts of classical mechanics^[1] are founded on some kind of a misinterpretation. Velocity is not a variable in our universe, there are only different local amounts of topological deformation to pass on.

figure 3

If the units within a region of space concentrate energy the whole transformation of the energy distribution is the redistribution of $\Delta V_{input} = \Delta V_{output}$ between the involved units. Every unit transfers 1 quantum of deformation during $1 t_c$ thus a concentration of energy – see figure 3 – is only conceivable if the pass on of the quanta is directed into some kind of a loop (termed "spin" for particles).

The concentration of the quanta of the involved units is expressed in Einstein's formula $E = m c^2$. Mass is the number of concentrated quanta and c^2 represents the action that is needed to transform every stored quantum of the mass (m) into *free quanta* again (E); quanta that have the velocity of the speed of light (c). But to concentrate quanta all the involved units transfer one or more fixed amounts of deformation – quanta – to the centre of the involved volume in space. The result is a decrease of the average surface area of all the units around the concentration in the centre (see figure 4, moving the blue arrows).

figure 4

So if I redistribute the stored quanta of the mass to the units around – to transform the stored quanta into free quanta – I have to increase the surface area of all the involved units. Because that is the result if I am increasing the topological deformation of every unit with 1 quantum. In other words, increasing the surface area of an invariant volume is like moving the red arrows in figure 4 synchronously. That is the meaning of Einstein's equation $E = m c^2$ inside discrete Euclidean space. In line with figure 3.

Reference:

1. T.W.B. Kible, F.H. Berkshire (2004), "*Classical Mechanics*"
Imperial College Press, ISBN 978-1-86094-435-2